

Coverage and Fronthaul Requirements in Beyond 5G C-RAN Deployments

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

With the advent of 5G, communication in the mmWave band (24-100 GHz) became one of the cornerstones of wireless communication research in the last years due to the large amount of available spectrum in said band, enabling the usage of bandwidths of up to 400 MHz [1]. Notably, operation in such bands entails a cell coverage shrinkage due to the worsening of the propagation conditions, partially compensated via beamforming techniques. Now, in advancing beyond 5G (B5G), the shift towards subTHz (90-300 GHz) and THz (0.3-10 THz) bands seems inevitable in order to harvest even broader bandwidths. This transition will further worsen channel conditions and shrink cell coverage, calling for Ultra-Dense Cell (UDC) deployments. In this work, we forecast frequency bands, communication bandwidths, antenna array sizes, and spatial multiplexing capabilities for B5G deployments to assess their impact on cell range and fronthaul (FH) capacity. Our work advances the state of the art in that it analyzes potential B5G configurations in terms of bandwidth, antenna, and layer numbers, as well as exploring non-standard functional splits (e.g., splits 7a, 7c, 7e). Fig. 1 shows the achievable signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) against the cell coverage range for the downlink (DL) of a cellular system operating at bands 3.5-90 GHz, with path-loss model in [2]. By example, to ensure a target SNR=10 dB, densification requirements increase from a cell range (distance between base station, BS, and user equipment, UE) of 800 m (3.5 GHz) to 150 m (90 GHz).

Fig. 1 SNR vs coverage range for different carrier frequencies (f_c).

Considering the above discussed context, Centralized Radio Access Network (C-RAN) architecture is foreseen to play a key role in future cellular systems [3], for the following key reasons. The first reason is identified in its ability to centralize and consolidate network infrastructure resources, significantly enhancing cost-effectiveness. Second, by centrally pooling baseband (BB) processing, it enhances radio resource management across multiple cells, improving overall network performance and allowing inter-cell coordination features. The functional split (“split” hereon), distributing BB processing functions between the centralized baseband unit (BBU) and the remote radio units (RRUs), is key in optimizing network performance, flexibility, and scalability in C-RAN (Fig. 2(a)). The split will determine the processing latency and workload between the BBU and RRUs, as well as the data traffic between the BBU and the RRUs over the FH. Thus, the dimensioning of the FH link becomes paramount, more so in higher frequency bands with increased bandwidth and antenna count, driving the FH data rates to unprecedented limits. Fig. 2(b) illustrates the estimated FH peak data rates for varying carrier frequency (f_c) and transmission bandwidth (B), as well as the antenna (N_{TRX}) and the layer (N_L) count, i.e. multiplexed UEs, considering several representative splits [3]. A peak analysis is considered, where the full bandwidth is allocated to UEs at the highest modulation and coding rates, considering the maximum number of spatially multiplexed UEs. As shown, the transition from the sub-6GHz band into the mmWave and THz era will challenge the adoption of a fully-centralized C-RAN (i.e., split 8) and will require new strategies in dealing with such unforeseen FH data rates. Such strategies may involve new splits which are more favourable in terms of lower transmission rates over the FH, as well as different FH compression control and optimization algorithms, dealing with packet scheduling strategies [4] and general optimization of parameters (e.g. bit quantization levels, precoding weight granularities, modulation order limitation) [5][6].

Fig. 2 (a) C-RAN architecture illustration with key units and fronthaul interconnect, (b) FH peak rates for several functional splits (6, 7e, 7c, 7a and 8).

Keywords: Centralized Radio Access Networks (C-RAN), wireless, fronthaul, THz, coverage, beyond 5G.

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